

Hybrid Model Engineering: A Residual Learning Approach for Modular AI Pipelines

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Abstract—Hybrid models combine first-principles knowledge with machine learning to enhance predictive performance while preserving physical consistency and interpretability. Despite their advantages, such approaches are often developed in a problem-specific manner and lack standardized workflows that support reuse and systematic experimentation. To address this challenge, this work proposes a modular, pipeline-based framework for hybrid model engineering within the Data Analytics and Visualization Environment (DAVE). The proposed Hybrid Model Engineering Engine (HMEE) integrates domain knowledge and machine learning components as configurable operators embedded in directed acyclic graph pipelines, enabling structured experimentation and lifecycle management within a unified platform. As a first representative hybrid strategy, residual learning is implemented and demonstrated in a real-world residential energy use case. A physics-informed thermal model provides baseline predictions, while a machine learning model learns to correct systematic deviations through residual modelling. The results illustrate how hybrid workflows can be engineered, executed, and evaluated in a structured and reproducible manner.

Index Terms—Hybrid Model Engineering, Science-Guided Machine Learning, Pipeline-Based Architectures, Residual Learning, MLOps

I. INTRODUCTION

Science based models (also known as first-principles models) have long been the primary tools for analyzing and optimizing complex systems [1]. These models rely on equations that govern physical processes and encode explicit cause-

effect relationships between input parameters and outputs. As a result, they provide interpretability and ensure physical consistency. However, their adoption in complex real-world settings is often limited. Such limitations mainly arise from partial knowledge of the underlying physical processes (model bias), calibration challenges due to parameter uncertainty or mis-specification, and the high computational cost associated with demanding simulations [2].

With the rapid growth of data availability and the development of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques capable of achieving high predictive performance, data-driven models have emerged as promising alternatives in various domains, including healthcare, materials science and climate modeling [3], [4], [5]. However, due to their black box nature, these models lack interpretability and may inherit bias from observational data, which can lead to poor generalization in unseen scenarios [2], [6]. To improve transparency, various post-hoc explainability methods have been proposed, providing insights into model behaviour through feature effect and feature importance analysis [7], [8], but remain detached from underlying physical processes.

To overcome these limitations of purely data-driven or physics-based models, a new paradigm has emerged, commonly referred to as hybrid models or science-guided machine learning [9]. The conceptual relationship between first-principles and data-driven approaches is illustrated in Fig 1.

These models aim to integrate scientific knowledge into machine learning approaches and have been applied in domains such as environmental applications and chemical engineering [1], [10].

Despite their advantages, engineering hybrid models in a structured and reusable way remains challenging. In contrast to conventional machine learning workflows, hybrid solutions are typically coupled with domain-specific knowledge, custom simulators, and problem-specific architectural choices. Developing, modifying, and experimenting with hybrid architectures involves coordinating multiple components and integrating physical constraints that vary across use cases.

Fig. 1: The spectrum between first-principles models and data-driven approaches

To address these challenges, this work introduces a modular framework for engineering hybrid models within a unified pipeline-based environment. This framework provides a structured way to define, configure, and evaluate hybrid strategies as reusable components, treating domain knowledge and machine learning modules as configurable operators. This design enables systematic experimentation and controlled comparison across alternative hybrid configurations.

The framework is implemented within the Data Analytics and Visualization Environment (DAVE), which provides orchestration and lifecycle management capabilities. On top of DAVE, we introduce the Hybrid Model Engineering Engine (HMEE), responsible for integrating simulator-based components and machine learning operators into coherent hybrid workflows. The first hybrid approach supported and structured within the HMEE is a residual learning strategy. To illustrate this approach, we report a residual learning experiment from a real-world energy use case provided by the domx IoT Technologies, highlighting the relevance of residual learning in practical scenarios.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A modular pipeline-based approach for the structured engineering of hybrid science-AI solutions, enabling reusable and configurable hybrid components, with the framework designed to accommodate multiple hybrid strategies.

- The design and implementation of the Hybrid Model Engineering Engine (HMEE), which integrates simulator and machine learning operators within the DAVE platform.
- The demonstration of a residual learning workflow on a real-world energy application, illustrating the relevance and applicability of this hybrid strategy.

II. CONTEXT AND BACKGROUND

A. AI-DAPT project

This work is developed in the context of the Horizon RIA project AI-DAPT, which aims to deliver trustworthy, reliable, and adaptable AI services through a data-centric AIOps framework. A key innovation of AI-DAPT is the integration of hybrid science-AI solutions that combine data-driven models with first-principles knowledge, validated across four application domains: health, robotics, energy, and manufacturing. DAVE and HMEE, presented in this work, support the structured implementation, training, and evaluation of hybrid AI solutions within this framework.

B. Hybrid Modelling in AI-DAPT

Based on recent literature on hybrid modelling, hybrid methods can be grouped into two main categories, depending on how domain knowledge and data-driven models are combined: (i) Science complements Machine Learning and (ii) Machine Learning complements Science [10].

In the Science-complements-ML category, domain knowledge directly constrains or guides the learning process. This may involve physics-guided feature engineering, where input features are selected or transformed to reflect known physical principles, and customized loss functions that impose hard or soft constraints (such as monotonicity constraint) to ensure physically consistent predictions [11], [12]. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), in which governing equations are embedded into the loss functions, are an example of this approach. PINNs have demonstrated success in solving forward and inverse problems involving ordinary and partial differential equations in areas such as fluid dynamics, heat transfer, and biomechanics [6], [13], [14]. In particular, solving inverse problems with PINNs is useful for parameter estimation, where unknown parameters or hidden variables are inferred from observational data under the constraints imposed by the governing equations, effectively integrating physical laws with data-driven approaches [15]. These methods are especially useful when governing equations are known, but available data are limited or noisy.

In the ML-complements-Science category, an existing physics-based or mechanistic model provides a primary approximation of the system, which is then refined or corrected by machine learning. Typical examples include surrogate modelling, where ML algorithms approximate the output of complex and computationally expensive physics-based simulations [16], [17], [18]. Another example is residual learning, where a simplified physics model provides an initial estimate and an ML model learns the residuals, the difference between

simplified predictions and real-world observations [10], [19]. Simulation-Based Inference (SBI) methods, which use simulation outputs for parameter estimation when direct likelihoods are intractable, also fall into this category [20], [21], [22].

The selection of hybrid strategy is determined by the characteristics of the problem at hand. Surrogate modelling is particularly useful when direct simulations are computationally prohibitive. Residual modelling is ideal when an approximate physical model exists and requires refinement. Methods like PINNs are effective when the governing equations of the physical process are well established. Across all these cases, the unifying principle is the integration of domain knowledge with machine learning to produce models that are not only accurate and efficient but also interpretable and physically consistent.

C. DAVE: Background and Framework

DAVE traces its origins to the Data Analytics Environment (DAE), a framework developed to address the challenge of making AI and data pipeline creation accessible to non-expert users in industrial settings [23]. DAE established the foundational architecture that DAVE builds upon combining a no-code/low-code approach with MLOps practices to enable the creation, orchestration, and lifecycle management of data-driven workflows. Built on top of Apache Airflow [24], which handles the underlying scheduling execution and monitoring of pipelines, DAE introduced a visual programming environment where users could compose analytical workflows by dragging and dropping operator blocks into a workspace, without requiring software development knowledge. These operators were organized into three functional categories: connectors, responsible for data ingestion from batch and streaming sources; transformers, covering data preparation and cleaning tasks; and analytics operators, encompassing machine learning algorithms and model management through MLflow.

A notable characteristic of the framework, carried forward into DAVE, is its extensibility through custom operators. Whenever a required functionality was absent from the built-in operator catalogue, users could extend the environment by supplying a Python script implementing the desired logic, an operator metadata file, and a unique name, allowing the new operator to be registered and used within pipelines just like any native one. This mechanism proved valuable in practice, as demonstrated in DAE’s validation in previous projects [23], where custom transformer operators were developed to handle factory-specific data formats that fell outside the scope of the standard catalogue.

Despite these capabilities, DAE’s iteration presented a key limitation acknowledged as future work: after defining a pipeline in the visual environment, users were required to navigate to the Apache Airflow interface separately to execute, schedule and monitor it, breaking the unified experience the platform otherwise offered. The evolution into DAVE addressed this gap by incorporating a dedicated Execution Environment directly within the platform, consolidating pipeline

definition, scheduling, execution monitoring and historical run tracking into a single, cohesive interface.

III. METHODS

A. HMEE in DAVE

DAVE enables the creation of hybrid models through its pipeline-based approach, allowing users to compose workflows using drag-and-drop operators that represent different functional components. In its current iteration, DAVE introduces a dedicated Execution Environment for scheduling, monitoring and tracking pipeline runs, as well as a model tracking interface where performance metrics, parameters and artifacts of trained models can be inspected, all within a single platform. Combined with an expanded operator framework that accommodates the specific computational components required for hybrid modelling, these capabilities act as key enablers for implementing HMEE workflows within DAVE.

Building upon these capabilities, HMEE is integrated into DAVE following a Service as Operator (SaO) approach. In this approach, hybrid modelling functionality is encapsulated as operators that are directly embedded within the pipeline structure, as internal steps of the overall Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG). The DAG structure, inherited from the underlying Apache Airflow orchestration layer, ensures deterministic execution order and prevents circular dependencies between operators, providing a reliable foundation for structured hybrid workflows. Hybrid workflows are therefore executed within the same environment as the rest of the pipeline, leveraging DAVE’s execution, scheduling, and monitoring mechanisms.

A key element of this integration is the ability to configure operators that participate in the hybrid workflow. Through their configuration interfaces, users can adjust model choices and operator-level parameters according to the requirements of each application. This functionality enables the design and evaluation of alternative hybrid pipeline structures and the exploration of different approaches without altering the overall pipeline logic. In the remainder of this paper, we focus on residual learning as the first hybrid approach, illustrating how hybrid approaches can be structured and executed in HMEE within a pipeline in DAVE.

B. Residual Learning in HMEE

Residual learning is a hybrid modelling strategy in which an ML model is used to correct the output of a physics-based simulator or a Reduced Order Model (ROM). The physics-based component captures the dominant system dynamics, but it typically relies on simplifying assumptions that may introduce systematic errors or approximation gaps. Rather than replacing the simulator, residual learning builds upon it by modelling the difference between simulated predictions and real-world observations, allowing data-driven methods to compensate for the limitations of the physical approximation.

Let y^{sim} denote the simulator output and y^{obs} the observed value. The residual is defined as:

$$r = y^{obs} - y^{sim} \quad (1)$$

The role of the ML component is to learn this correction term and improve the final prediction. In practice, the final corrected prediction is obtained as $\hat{y} = y^{sim} + \hat{r}$, where the ML model is trained to approximate r from the available observations. In this way, the simulator provides a physically grounded baseline estimate, while the ML model captures the remaining discrepancy between simulation and reality. Depending on the implementation, this can be achieved by explicitly learning the residual r defined in (1), or by training an ML model that directly predicts the corrected output while using the simulator prediction as an additional input variable.

Within the HMEE, residual learning is implemented as a structured pipeline following DAG logic. The simulator operator receives the initial dataset and augments it with the simulated predictions, producing an enriched dataset that contains both observed and simulated values. This enriched dataset is then passed to the ML operator, which provides the final corrected outputs. This sequential structure enables a clear separation between the physics-based and data-driven components, while ensuring their consistent integration within the same framework. In the current implementation, the simulator remains static during pipeline execution with no feedback from the ML stage; it is first executed to produce baseline predictions, and the ML model subsequently learns to correct the residuals. The overall residual learning workflow, including simulator and ML operators within the HMEE is illustrated in Fig. 2.

To implement the residual learning approach in practice, the pipeline is structured around two main types of configurable operators that realize the hybrid workflow:

1) *Domain Knowledge Component (Simulator Operators)*: Within the residual pipeline, the domain component is implemented through simulator operators integrated into the DAVE environment. Simulators represent mechanistic models that provide predictions before the data-driven correction step.

In DAVE, simulators are treated as configurable operators that can be incorporated into a pipeline through a drag-and-drop interface. The user can select a simulator from an available list of simulator operators. Once added, a configuration panel allows the user to define the simulator’s parameter values prior to execution.

The available simulators are integrated into the platform through HMEE. In addition to these predefined simulators, DAVE provides a dedicated simulator interface that enables users to upload their own simulator implementations (Fig. 3). Through this interface, the user specifies the simulator name and uploads a Python script and provides JSON configuration that defines simulator parameters. The JSON configuration serves as a structured template for specifying the parameter types and their default values. Importantly, the Python script must implement a function that receives the initial dataset as a DataFrame, ensuring consistent communication between operators in the pipeline. Upon execution, the simulator processes this dataset and produces an enriched DataFrame that contains the original features with the simulated values. This enriched dataset serves as output of the simulator operator.

The simulation parameters are generally categorized into two groups. Basic parameters correspond to the core physical quantities or constants that define the physical process. In the current implementation, these parameters are assumed to be known and are kept fixed during pipeline execution. In future extensions, parameter estimation could be incorporated to learn these values from the data, supporting scenarios where parameters are initially unknown. Advanced parameters refer to the execution-related settings required for running the simulation, such as the simulation horizon or initial conditions.

The enriched dataset produced by the simulator, containing both the original features and the simulated predictions, can serve as the input to the subsequent ML operator. In this way, the physics-based baseline model is systematically integrated into the pipeline and directly coupled with the data-driven correction stage.

2) *ML Component (ML Operators)*: ML operators in HMEE belong to the analytics operator category within DAVE and represent the data-driven component of hybrid pipelines. In the residual pipeline, the ML operator receives the enriched dataset produced by the simulator operator. The user can configure ML operator to employ a variety of algorithms, including decision trees, random forest, gradient boosting methods (LightGBM, XGBoost, CatBoost), linear models, or sequential models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs). Hyperparameters such as learning rate, epochs, tree depth, or other-specific parameters can be adjusted allowing flexible experimentation. Once trained, the ML operator produced the corrected predictions that refine simulator outputs, effectively implementing the residual learning logic in practice.

The HMEE architecture enables users to integrate multiple ML operators within the same pipeline, run them sequentially or in parallel, and systematically evaluate their performance. Metrics from each execution are recorded in MLflow and within DAVE interface, allowing users to compare models, analyze results, and select the best performing configuration. In Fig. 4, the residual learning pipeline in HMEE is illustrated using a version of the thermal heating simulator that domx provided, and different ML operators, highlighting modular integration within the workflow.

IV. ENERGY USE CASE DEMONSTRATION

A. Problem Statement

Natural gas condensing boilers are widely used in residential buildings providing heating and domestic hot water. In our scenario, we are interested in predicting the indoor temperature (T_z) of a building and key boiler related features, such as the water supply temperature (T_s), and the water return temperature (T_r). To achieve this, we use a physics-based model based on [25], to predict the system temperatures and an RNN that maps temperatures to boiler modulation (blr_{mod_lvl}) and consequently to thermal power. The physics-based model, combined with the RNN that estimates the boiler modulation, predict the three state temperatures. These predictions are then

Fig. 2: Residual learning pipeline in HMEE

Add New Simulator

Simulator Name

Enter simulator name

Simulator Parameters (JSON)

Enter a valid list of JSON objects ({"key1": value1}, {"key2": value2}) · E.g: [{"name": "parameter_name", "pres_name": "Parameter Name", "description": "Description of the parameter", "type": "Parameter data type (e.g., string, integer, float)", "default": "default value for the parameter, "accepted_values": [list of accepted values for enum types, types, optional] }]

Upload Simulator Script File

Fig. 3: Add Simulator Interface

refined by an ML model through a residual learning approach, which corrects the discrepancies between the simulator outputs and observed values.

B. Example Dataset and Preprocessing

For our experimentation, a dataset concerning the period from November 2024 to February 2025 was collected from a residential building consisting of various sensor measurements as described in Table I. The dataset variables are mapped to model notation as follows: T_s for supply water temperature (“blr_t”), T_r for return water temperature (“t_ret”), T_z for indoor temperature (“t_r”) and T_{amb} for outdoor temperature (“t_out”).

TABLE I: Dataset Features

Feature	Description
t_out	Outdoor temperature
t_set	Supply water setpoint of the boiler
blr_t	Supply water temperature
t_ret	Return water temperature
t_r	Indoor zone temperature
blr_mod_lvl	Boiler modulation level
water	Boolean indicating DHW

The measurements were resampled to a 5-minute resolution, and any data points, where the Domestic Hot Water (DHW) flag was true, were removed. DHW events affect the supply and return water temperature as well as the boiler modulation activity and produce effects irrelevant to the demand for space heating, which is signaled by a non-zero t_{set} value. The supply water setpoint t_{set} is generated by an external Proportional-Integral (PI) controller. In this experiment t_{set} along with T_{amb}

are treated as known exogenous signals. Finally, the data were split chronologically into training (70%), validation (15%) and testing (15%) sets.

C. Reduced Order Thermal Model

To simulate the evolution of the indoor, supply and return water temperature we rely on reduced order model (ROM), governed by the following system of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs):

$$C_s \frac{dT_s}{dt} = k_{sr}(T_r - T_s) + Q_{out} \quad (2)$$

$$C_r \frac{dT_r}{dt} = k_{sr}(T_s - T_r) + k_{rz}(T_z - T_r) \quad (3)$$

$$C_z \frac{dT_z}{dt} = k_{rz}(T_r - T_z) + k_{za}(T_{amb} - T_z), \quad (4)$$

where C_s , C_r , and C_z represent the thermal capacitances and k_{sr} , k_{rz} , and k_{za} the thermal conductances respectively, whereas Q_{out} and T_{amb} represent the thermal power and outdoor temperature. All thermal parameters are parametrized in log space, and since they are non-negative, their value is retrieved by exponentiating at each forward pass. The resulting capacitances and conductances are treated as effective values obtained by fitting the model to operational data. After time discretization using the Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) method, the system can be written in state space form:

$$x[k+1] = Ax[k] + Bu[k], \quad (5)$$

where A and B are matrices, x is the vector of the states and u is the input vector. Since thermal output (Q_{out}) is not measured directly, we model it with a GRU network. Specifically, at each step the network uses as input the current supply and return water temperature and t_{set} , and outputs a boiler modulation signal between 0% and 100%, which along with the water return temperature is used to estimate the thermal output using the relationship:

$$Q_{out} = \frac{m}{100} \cdot Q_{max} \cdot \eta(T_r), \quad (6)$$

where m denotes boiler modulation, Q_{max} is the assumed nominal input capacity, and $\eta(\cdot)$ is a nominal condensing boiler efficiency curve depending on return water temperature. The combined ROM and GRU model constitute the simulator.

D. Simulator/baseline model training

In order to learn the six parameters of the state space model and the parameters of the GRU network, we use a sliding window approach where each window, consisting

Fig. 4: Residual learning workflow in HMEE using DAVE: (a) pipeline integrating a thermal model provided by DOMX with CatBoost, XGBoost and Random Forest models; (b) CatBoost operator configuration panel.

of N timesteps, is extracted from continuous segments. At each window the state is initialized from measurements. A description of a step of the forward path can be found in Fig. 5.

Instead of learning all the parameters (both for the model and the GRU) at once, we split training into stages. Specifically, in the first stage, the GRU’s parameters remain frozen, whereas the state space model’s parameters are learnable. Measured modulation and measured return water temperature are used to compute Q_{out} and the parameters are optimized such that the multistep temperature prediction error is minimized over the sliding windows. In the second stage, the state space model’s parameters are frozen and the GRU is trained by supervised learning to reproduce the measured boiler modulation from measured supply temperature, return temperature, and the observed water supply setpoint t_{set} . In the final stage, all parameters are jointly updated with the models relying on their own predicted values. The GRU observes the model’s predicted temperatures and produces a modulation signal. This signal along with the return water temperature determines Q_{out} which is used as input to the state space model to produce the next step temperature predictions. No measured signals are used in the loop apart from the outdoor weather temperature, which is considered to be known, and t_{set} .

E. Baseline model Evaluation

The test set consists of multiple continuous segments of varying length, and the model is evaluated on each segment separately. For each segment, the state (T_s, T_r, T_z) is initialized from the first measured timestep, after which the model is rolled out using only the outdoor temperature and t_{set} as exogenous inputs. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error

(MAPE) are computed separately for each continuous test segment and for each predicted variable. The values reported in Table II are the mean \pm standard deviation of these segment level metrics across test segments. Therefore, the standard deviation reflects variability among test segments. MAPE is not reported for the modulation signal, since the true values are often zero (when there is no modulation activity). Division by near zero true values produces large percentage errors that do not reflect meaningful prediction quality.

TABLE II: Baseline Model Metrics

Metric	T_s	T_r	T_z	mod
RMSE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	4.46 ± 0.92	3.35 ± 1.00	0.37 ± 0.22	4.39 ± 1.08
MAE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3.20 ± 0.59	2.59 ± 0.65	0.31 ± 0.19	2.12 ± 0.77
MAPE (%)	10.7 ± 2.2	9.8 ± 2.9	1.5 ± 1.0	–

Note: RMSE and MAE for modulation are in percentage points.

F. Residual Correction

The state space model cannot capture complex thermal building dynamics, since it is a reduced order model. This simplification means that several effects such as solar gains, when sunlight enters through the windows and heats the zone directly, internal gains due to heat released by occupants or appliances, and nonlinear effects are not captured, especially affecting the prediction for the indoor temperature. All these factors compromise the accuracy of the state space model.

To tackle this, we propose a residual correction mechanism based on CatBoost [26] a gradient boosting method. Since our primary objective is to improve the prediction accuracy on the three outputs, the water supply, the water return and the indoor temperature, we use CatBoost’s native multi-output regression with the MultiRMSE loss, so that a single model jointly predicts the three residual targets.

Fig. 5: Forward path step

Following the residual learning formulation (Eq. 1), the residual target is defined as the difference between the measured state and the simulator state. In the current implementation, CatBoost is trained as a one-step-ahead residual corrector. For each timestep k , a feature vector ϕ_k is constructed from the current exogenous variables, time encodings, simulator outputs, simulated modulation, lagged outdoor temperatures and rolling outdoor temperature statistics. The residual target corresponds to the simulator error at the next timestep:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{s,k+1} &= T_{s,k+1}^{obs} - T_{s,k+1}^{sim}, \\ r_{r,k+1} &= T_{r,k+1}^{obs} - T_{r,k+1}^{sim}, \\ r_{z,k+1} &= T_{z,k+1}^{obs} - T_{z,k+1}^{sim}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $T_s^{sim}, T_r^{sim}, T_z^{sim}$ are the simulator outputs and $T_s^{obs}, T_r^{obs}, T_z^{obs}$ the measured values. The CatBoost model is then trained to predict these residuals, and the final corrected predictions are obtained as $\hat{T} = T^{sim} + \hat{r}$. It should be noted that the corrected state is not fed back into the simulator during rollout. The configuration used to train the model was: MultiRMSE loss, 2000 maximum iterations, learning rate 0.05, depth 6, L_2 leaf regularization 3.0, early stopping after 100 validation iterations, and random seed 42.

The metrics are aggregated across test segments as in Table II and reported in Table III.

TABLE III: Residual Model Metrics

Metric	T_s	T_r	T_z
RMSE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3.34 ± 0.87	2.69 ± 0.79	0.31 ± 0.13
MAE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	2.48 ± 0.57	2.10 ± 0.57	0.26 ± 0.12
MAPE (%)	7.9 ± 2.0	7.3 ± 2.2	1.3 ± 0.6

G. Purely Data Driven Baseline

To compare the residual learning approach against a purely data driven approach, we train a GRU based model. The model receives the current thermal state (T_s, T_r, T_z) and the exogenous inputs (T_{amb}, t_{set}) , and predicts the next-step temperatures (T_s, T_r, T_z) . The GRU baseline is trained for one step ahead prediction and during testing, the model is rolled out recursively from the same initial measured state and on the same continuous test segments as the simulator. The metrics are aggregated across test segments as in Tables II and III and are reported in Table IV.

TABLE IV: Data Driven Model Metrics

Metric	T_s	T_r	T_z
RMSE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3.54 ± 1.04	3.14 ± 0.79	0.39 ± 0.18
MAE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	2.77 ± 0.67	2.50 ± 0.62	0.33 ± 0.16
MAPE (%)	8.98 ± 1.98	8.74 ± 2.07	1.66 ± 0.84

The setpoint for the supply water temperature t_{set} is generated by a PI controller that acts on the error between the measured indoor temperature and the user defined comfort setpoint. In this setting t_{set} is considered to be known. Therefore, the reported results evaluate the temperature prediction conditional on the observed controller trajectory. As future work, this dependency could be removed by incorporating a surrogate model that predicts t_{set} by comparing the predicted indoor temperature with the user defined comfort setpoint. Furthermore, in the current residual correction paradigm the simulator does not interact with the model used for residual learning. An alternative direction would be to incorporate "Solver-in-the-Loop" approaches as in [27], where the corrected state is recurrently used into a Partial Differential Equation (PDE) solver across multiple unrolled steps. This allows the neural network to interact continuously with the evolution of the differential equation. Additionally, it would be interesting to explore alternative approaches such as the methodology presented in [28] and the subsequent work [29], where physical consistency is achieved by design. In their approach, the parameters of the simulator consisting of a physics inspired module based on Resistance-Capacitance (RC) dynamics and a black box module are jointly learned. Physical consistency is guaranteed through a careful architectural decomposition of temperature dynamics into an unforced nonlinear component and an energy accumulator component.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Answering Research Questions

This work investigates whether hybrid AI solutions can be engineered in a structured and reusable way through a modular pipeline-based framework. The proposed HMEE demonstrates that this is feasible by integrating simulator and machine learning components as configurable operators within a unified workflow environment. This design enables users to systematically define, execute, and evaluate hybrid pipelines, while preserving the flexibility required by different application domains. By treating simulators and ML models as independent pipeline components, users can replace, reconfigure, or extend individual operators without modifying the overall workflow logic, enabling systematic experimentation with alternative hybrid configurations.

In this context, residual learning serves as the first representative hybrid strategy supported by HMEE. The residual learning workflow described above combines a simulator operator that provides baseline predictions with an ML operator that learns to correct the residual error between simulated outputs and observed measurements. This structure demonstrates how hybrid model strategies can be operationalized within

the proposed framework while preserving the physical prior knowledge encoded in the simulator.

The energy use case presented in this work illustrates this hybrid modelling logic in practice, following the pipeline-based design presented in Section III. The simulator captures the main temperatures dynamics of the heating system across three state variables: the supply water (T_s), the return water temperature (T_r), and the indoor temperature (T_z). The residual learning component then improves these predictions by modelling discrepancies between simulator output and observed data. The results demonstrate an improvement in prediction accuracy across all three variables following residual correction relative to the simulator baseline. The purely data driven baseline achieves reasonable accuracy indicating that the model can capture part of the dynamics. However, any comparison between the purely data driven model and the hybrid should be interpreted together with the qualitative advantage of the latter. The simulator preserves an explicit thermal structure and physically interpretable heat transfer pathway, while the CatBoost residual model corrects systematic deviations from measured data. This energy use case demonstrates the applicability of the HMEE design for supporting residual learning workflows, highlighting how the proposed pipeline structure can systematically integrate physics-based models with data-driven corrections.

Although this work focuses on residual learning, the HMEE architecture is designed to accommodate additional hybrid strategies. For instance, surrogate modelling can be supported within the same operator-based workflow structure, where ML operators are trained to approximate simulator outputs. Experimental validation of surrogate workflows, however, depends on the availability of suitable simulators across the current AI-DAPT application domains.

It is important to note that the current implementation of the HMEE assumes that the simulator parameters remain fixed during pipeline execution. Although the energy use case presented in this work involves a parameter estimation procedure for the thermal model, this training step is performed offline and is not yet integrated into the HMEE pipeline. Instead, the simulator is treated as a predefined domain knowledge component whose outputs are subsequently refined through the residual learning strategy.

A natural extension of this work is the integration of parameter estimation capabilities within the HMEE, enabling simulator parameters to become learnable through optimization algorithms. Supporting such functionality would allow hybrid workflows, where the physics-based model itself can be systematically calibrated within the pipeline, further expanding the range of hybrid modelling strategies supported by the platform.

B. Match and contribution

Addressing the Management of Emerging Technology. Hybrid AI is an emerging technological paradigm with growing relevance across industrial domains. However, current hybrid solutions are often developed in a problem-specific

manner, requiring integration of domain knowledge, simulators, and architectural choices, making systematic reuse and experimentation across domains difficult. This work addresses this challenge by proposing a structured engineering framework for hybrid workflows.

Providing Practical Frameworks. HMEE translates hybrid AI concepts into an operational workflow that supports experimentation, execution, and evaluation within a single platform. By integrating pipeline orchestration, experiment tracking, and configurable hybrid operators, the framework reduces the engineering effort typically required to develop and compare hybrid solutions across different application settings.

Analyzing Implementation Challenges. A key challenge during the development of HMEE was accommodating the level of customization required by different hybrid workflows while preserving a reusable architecture. Different applications may require domain-specific simulator, data transformations, or training strategies. To address this, HMEE supports custom operators and user-defined components, highlighting the broader challenge of balancing flexibility with standardization in hybrid model engineering.

Focusing on Value Creation. The proposed framework reduces the complexity of designing and experimenting with hybrid AI systems by providing reusable pipeline components and integrated execution management. This improves reproducibility, reduces integration overhead, and enables systematic comparison of alternative hybrid configurations. In the energy use case, this facilitates structured evaluation of residual learning workflows, leading to improved predictive performance while preserving physical consistency.

VI. CONCLUSION

Hybrid modelling remains a challenging task due to the diverse architectures, requirements, and domain-specific knowledge that different solutions demand. In this work, we have implemented the residual learning approach within the HMEE framework in a modular fashion, where distinct operators handle specific functionalities and can be easily replaced, enabling users to experiment with alternative pipeline configurations. Currently, simulator parameters are fixed and learning them through optimization is not yet supported, but this functionality is planned for future extensions. Overall, this implementation demonstrates how a structured, operator-based platform can facilitate the design, integration, and evaluation of hybrid models in a consistent and reproducible manner.

This work is developed within the AI-DAPT project, demonstrating how hybrid science-AI solutions can be systematically engineered and evaluated in the context of real-world applications. Hybrid models offer a powerful approach to combining domain knowledge with machine learning, producing results that are both interpretable and effective. Residual learning serves as a representative strategy in this context, and HMEE provides a first step toward a platform that can accommodate a variety of hybrid architectures. Future work includes extending the framework to other use cases within AI-DAPT, such as health, robotics, and manufacturing, as

well as introducing parameter estimation and surrogate modelling pipelines. These enhancements will allow more sophisticated hybrid strategies, supporting users in both designing new workflows and refining model components automatically, while maintaining the modularity and flexibility of the overall pipeline.

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